

Thermal coupling and interface design of a hybrid nuclear system for hydrogen production

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ABSTRACT

Among the most promising features of advanced Generation IV reactors, their enhanced integrability with innovative technologies supporting the energy transition is often highlighted. The main plant modifications, technical requirements, and broader implications are investigated in this study. Specifically, the energy conversion system of a lead-cooled fast reactor (LFR) has been implemented in combination with the thermal interface required for the integration with a high-temperature electrolysis hydrogen production plant. Solid oxide electrolysis (SOE) technology emerges as the most promising option in terms of efficiency and scalability, as it is capable of exploiting both the thermal and electrical power generated by the nuclear system. Focusing on the steam cycle and the interface with the hydrogen production plant, the most effective combinations of heat extraction and reinjection points are identified, and an appropriate sizing of the intermediate circuit for heat transfer and of the hydrogen production unit is proposed. Finally, the most critical components and parameters affecting the coupling are highlighted and analyzed to ensure reliability and flexibility of the integrated system.

Keywords: Nuclear cogeneration, Lead Cooled Fast Reactor, High Temperature Steam Electrolysis, Steam extraction points

1. INTRODUCTION

In the context of the energy transition, hydrogen is emerging as a key energy carrier for the decarbonization of heavy industry, transportation, and as a means to support electrical grids. However, the overall sustainability of hydrogen-based projects strongly depends on the production pathway adopted. Among the technologies with the lowest environmental impact, water electrolysis stands out, particularly in its high-temperature configuration, due to its superior efficiency compared to alternative processes [1]. Since it requires both electrical and thermal power, this technology is well suited for integration with a cogenerative nuclear power plant. However, the term high temperature in relation to the electrolysis process sometimes leads to the assumption that the thermal input required by the process must necessarily be in the order of 650–800°C. This is strictly true from the standpoint of the electrolysis cell, which must indeed be maintained at such temperatures to operate properly, but it is not the case at system level. Aside from minor losses compensated by electric heaters, the majority of the required thermal power is associated with the vaporization of the feed water and for an initial superheating thanks to a system of heat recuperators.

Evaporation temperatures close to ambient conditions therefore make it possible to extend the coupling to reactor types other than advanced gas cooled reactors, which have so far been the main focus of analyses on nuclear-based hydrogen production [2]. Although water-cooled reactors are, in principle, compatible with SOE applications, this study is applied to ALFRED (Advanced Lead-cooled Fast Reactor European Demonstrator), a Generation IV reactor. Since 2013, the FALCON consortium, led by

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Ansaldò Nucleare, ENEA, and RATEN-ICN, has cooperated on developing this lead-cooled fast reactor (LFR) concept, continuously advancing its design toward the subsequent commercial-scale reactor EAGLES-300, scheduled for realization by 2039. The selection of ALFRED is motivated by the fact that, over the years, research activities have consistently extended beyond the plant's capability to meet electrical grid demand [3]. The potential for cogenerative applications has always represented a key advantage with hydrogen production being a promising opportunity. The integration between reactor technology and Solid Oxide Electrolysis (SOE) has been the topic of several research studies, mainly interested in the coupling approach in design conditions [4]. Most of them assumed extraction and reinjection points without deepening the investigation of alternatives [5]. The present study aims to design a hybrid system integrating a nuclear power plant with a large-scale hydrogen production facility, analyzing the impact of a wide range of steam extraction points. A major effort is devoted to investigating off-design conditions, highlighting also the impact on an intermediate heat transfer loop.

This work is organized as follows. In Section 2, the integrated plant configuration and models are presented. The thermodynamic analysis carried out to compare and identify the most suitable combination of steam extraction and reinjection points is detailed in Section 3.1. The selected configuration is then presented in Section 3.2, while the results of the off-design analysis are reported in Section 3.3, assessing the plant's performance under varying hydrogen demand, which corresponds to different thermal power transfer from the nuclear steam cycle to the hydrogen section.

2. STEAM CYCLE MODELING

2.1. BOP architecture and modeling approach

The Balance of Plant (BOP) of an integrated nuclear plant is responsible for allocating the heat extracted from the reactor either to electrical power generation or to cogenerative applications. Since this work focuses on assessing the capability of the energy conversion system to operate in coupled mode with a cogeneration technology, the analysis initially concentrated on steady-state design conditions. To define the plant architecture, *Epsilon Professional* is employed, a tool for modeling, simulating, and optimizing complex thermodynamic cycles [6]. Using this software, the reference configuration—intended solely for electricity generation—is first developed. Several BOP variants are then derived, incorporating different heat extraction and reinjection points, as well as the corresponding intermediate circuit required for heat exchange with external users. For the reference BOP, the guidelines provided by the ANSELMUS project are adopted to ensure compliance with the specific structural and safety constraints of the selected reactor [7]. The most critical aspects refer to the steam generator (SG) whose secondary-side fluid temperature is limited to 335°C for the feedwater inlet and to 450°C for the superheated steam at the outlet. Although the ALFRED project foresees a three-stage development approach, characterized by progressively increasing thermal power levels, these values refer to the third and final stage version [8]. Based on these boundaries, a Rankine steam cycle was implemented in *Epsilon*, with its main parameters summarized in Table I.

Table I. ALFRED balance of plant main parameters [7].

Parameter	Value	Unit
Thermal input	300	MW _{th}
SG inlet/outlet temperature	335/450	°C
SG pressure	185	bar
HP turbine inlet/outlet pressure	180/37	bar
IP turbine inlet/outlet pressure	36.5/3	bar
LP turbine inlet/outlet pressure	3/0.09	bar

In Figure 1, the layout of the BOP is displayed. Each feedwater pre-heater (FWH) is modeled to deliver saturated liquid at the outlet of the hot leg and to recirculate part of the condensate toward the preceding, lower-pressure heat exchanger. A crucial role is played by the final FWH, located immediately upstream of the steam generator inlet and tasked with maintaining the feedwater temperature as close as possible to its nominal design value by a controlled mass flow of live steam. The resulting cycle enables a gross electric output exceeding $125 \text{ MW}_{\text{el}}$, which corresponds to a gross efficiency of around 42%, in full agreement with ALFRED project results [8]. An intermediate loop is also represented, composed by two heat exchangers and an aftercooler, whose function is detailed in Section 2.3.

Figure 1. Balance of plant layout of the hybrid nuclear system with an illustrative steam extraction configuration and an intermediate loop.

2.2. Off-design modeling

Extracting heat by withdrawing a portion of the working fluid from a BOP system originally designed for electricity generation introduces additional operational modes in which the plant can function. Each analysis involving steam extraction from the BOP is therefore conducted under off-design conditions. However, regardless of the specific operating state, certain variables must be maintained as close as possible to their respective design values, to ensure component integrity and safe operation. These include the outlet pressure and temperature of the steam from the SG, the pressure along the moisture separation and reheating (MSR) line, the pressure in the deaerator (DEA), and the hot-side temperature of the intermediate circuit. Given the decision to minimize the use of control and regulation features within the *Epsilon* modeling tool, this set of variables is imposed as fixed boundary condition. All other points in the thermodynamic cycle are instead calculated under off-design conditions. Steam turbines that experience variations in the internal mass flow rate are modeled according to Stodola's cone law. Similarly, the tool provides characteristic curves that represent the efficiency behavior of components as a function of specific parameters, e.g., the mass flow rate. Variable efficiency is also associated with all heat exchangers, pumps, and turbines retaining the default off-design performance characteristics available in the code.

2.3. SOE and thermal interconnection design requirements

SOE cells are electrochemical devices suitable to perform water electrolysis at high temperature, which implies intrinsic better performance than the corresponding low-temperature technologies, due to faster

kinetics and higher conductivity [9]. Cells are usually arranged in series within stacks and, in turn, grouped into modules in order to achieve the order of MW_{el} of power, which is consistent with industrial-level hydrogen production rates. The electrochemical reduction of steam occurs on a negatively charged cathode, releasing hydrogen and O^{2-} ions. The ions are conducted through the solid oxide electrolyte towards the positively charged anode, where they recombine into molecular oxygen. Each module of the electrolyzer is equipped with a system of heat recuperators that enable the exploitation of the hot hydrogen and oxygen streams exiting the stacks to preheat the incoming steam and air streams. As the nuclear plant is supposed to be entirely dedicated to hydrogen production, the hydrogen plant capacity is sized according to the availability of electricity supply from the steam cycle, taking into account the flow rate reduction due to the steam extraction. In parallel, to vaporize the feedwater in the SOE section, an intermediate circuit is foreseen that transfers thermal power from the steam cycle. This allows also the hydrogen production facility to be installed at a certain distance from the nuclear plant, and to avoid phase change on both sides of the heat exchanger. The chosen intermediate loop fluid is Dowtherm A, a synthetic organic heat transfer fluid stable up to $400^{\circ}C$. Referring to Figure 1, the vapor extracted from the steam cycle is condensed in the heat exchanger called 'Top', sub-cooled in the 'Aftercooler' and then throttled so it can be returned to the cycle. The heat is transported by the intermediate fluid to the 'Bottom' heat exchanger, where it is supplied to the SOE feedwater for evaporation and superheating up to $150^{\circ}C$. In principle, the heating steam can be extracted from virtually any point within the BOP; however, each location is characterized by distinct and almost unique thermodynamic conditions. Consequently, no single extraction point can optimally satisfy every possible cogenerative application at the same time—the selection must be tailored to the specific thermal requirements of the end-user. In this case, to ensure a sufficient margin, a minimum extraction steam temperature of $240^{\circ}C$ is imposed that corresponds to any steam point upstream of the IP turbines. The selection of the optimal extraction configuration is detailed in Section 3.

In conclusion, the circuit sizing is dependent on the electrolyzer capacity, as its components are designed to transfer the required thermal energy while respecting the pinch point constraints. Specific energy consumptions of $39 \text{ kWh}_{el}/\text{kg}_{H2}$ and $8.43 \text{ kW}_{th}/\text{kg}_{H2}$ are assumed for the SOE module [1]. The intermediate circuit pump consumption is also taken into account, even though it has a minor effect on cycle performance and on the sizing of the electrolyser. Because the cells may be located away from the nuclear plant, thermal losses are considered: 80 W/m in the hot leg and 60 W/m in the cold leg over a 1 km distance, leading to an intermediate fluid temperature drop of about $1^{\circ}C$ between the top and bottom heat exchangers [10].

3. RESULTS

3.1. Steam extraction and re-injection points

A comparative analysis is carried out to assess the plant's production capacity, regardless of the specific non-electric application, as a function of the extraction and reinjection points, assuming fixed extracted thermal powers and a water return temperature of $200^{\circ}C$. A set of extraction points is investigated, starting from the live steam line and progressively moving toward lower pressure points. In correspondence with the high-pressure expansion stages, the amount of steam extracted is relatively small (Figure 2, center); however, the higher is the extraction pressure the worse is the impact on the electric power generation (Figure 2, left). As the extraction moves toward lower-pressure stages, the removed mass flow increases, consistent with the decreasing enthalpy content, while the net electrical output rises. At the outlet of the reheater, the required steam drops sharply due to its superheated state, but the electrical output continues to increase, reaching its maximum values at the first IP stages. It is worth noting that the choice of extraction point has a minor impact at low extracted thermal powers, while it becomes increasingly significant as the degree of cogeneration grows. From approximately 40 MW_{th} onward, the gap between the maximum and minimum achievable net electric output exceeds 10

Figure 2. BOP net electrical production (left and right figures) and extracted steam mass flow (middle figure) as function of different extraction and reinjection points.

MW_{el}. In addition, extracting steam from the same turbine stage does not guarantee that the quality of the stream remains constant regardless of the amount extracted. A direct consequence of reducing the steam flow through the turbine is a decrease in the extraction pressure. This leads to an increasingly steep rise in the required flow rate as the extraction flow decreases, as shown in Figure 2, where each point corresponds to a fixed extraction location within the BOP. At the same time, this behavior implies that the nominal flow (prior to extraction) experiences a larger pressure drop during expansion, resulting in larger electrical output. This provides a first explanation for the nonlinear trend observed in the variation of net electrical output with respect to the extracted thermal power. In fact, it is interesting to observe that as more thermal power is extracted, the relative impact on the conversion performance of the BOP becomes smaller. Also, removing part of the steam flow upstream to the MSR reduces the load on the reheater while reinjecting it downstream of the low-pressure FWHs allows a reduction in the steam bleed from the IP and LP turbines as well as a reduced load for the condensate pump. Ultimately, this results in a net gain in electrical power at the generator. Regarding the reinjection conditions, the plant performance varies only slightly with the selected point, with the sole exception of reinjecting to the condenser, which tends to show the lowest performance as the extracted thermal power increases. In Figure 2 (right) the electric output is shown with respect to five different reinjection points (inlet of condenser, low-pressure FWHs and deaerator) when live steam is extracted. The possibility of returning water downstream of the high-pressure feedwater pump was also investigated by including a reinjection pump. The results show slightly better performances only in the case of extraction from the steam generator outlet, given the lower pressure restoration required. In the following, extractions directly from turbine stages are excluded. Instead, attention was focused on the possibility of diverting steam from the turbine admission and reheating lines. This choice is motivated by the fact that turbine extractions are generally uncontrolled, with the extracted mass flow only depending on the downstream pressure. In contrast, by extracting steam from the chosen lines, thermal power can be regulated by introducing appropriate valves. Based on these considerations, three extraction points were identified:

- At the outlet of the steam generator, at high pressure and temperature (HP/HT, 183 bar / 450°C);
- At the outlet of the high-pressure turbine, at intermediate pressure and low temperature (IP/LT, 37 bar / 246°C);
- At the outlet of the moisture separator and reheater, at intermediate pressure and high temperature (IP/HT, 37 bar / 353°C).

Each extraction point requires a corresponding return point, determined by the fluid conditions after heat exchange with the intermediate loop. Two reinjection points are considered:

- At the condenser inlet (COND);
- Along the main feedwater line, at the inlet of the deaerator (DEA).

3.2. Impact of interface points on the integrated system sizing

Not all combinations of extraction and return points yield the same level of performance. Certain pairings may introduce technical or thermodynamic constraints that must be carefully addressed and therefore, an off-design analysis is performed at progressively higher extracted thermal power. Although in all cases the electric power output decreases almost proportionally with the extracted steam flow rate, the IP/LT extraction point appears to be the one capable of maintaining the highest net output for the same amount of extracted thermal power. This is a direct consequence of the fact that the mass flow rate expanding through the high-pressure turbine stages does not remain constant but slightly increases as the bleed to feed the reheaters lowers. Coming from the steam generator and the high pressure turbine stage, that saved amount of steam can instead be expanded in the turbine. This effect, although beneficial from a performance standpoint, is limited to low extracted thermal powers, since an excessive increase in flow rate through the first turbine stages causes an excessive rise in the inlet pressure. At the cost of minimal efficiency loss, this effect is completely avoided when steam is extracted at the IP/HT point, as the steam flow to be superheated in the reheater remains constant regardless of the extracted thermal power. Finally, the HP/HT point, due to its higher enthalpy content, allows a reduced extracted flow for the same thermal power but exhibits the most detrimental effects on turbine performance, with a significantly lower electrical output compared to the previous two cases. In terms of the analyzed reinjection points, returning steam directly to the condenser is the least thermodynamically efficient option. Reinjecting it upstream of the deaerator reduces the load on the low-pressure feedwater line, offering a relatively better performance. However, the deaerator is sensitive to fluctuations in pressure and temperature, and the reinjection process must be properly regulated. Controlling the return temperature and keeping it below specific thresholds is, therefore, crucial and leads to the inclusion of a subcooling section in the 'Aftercooler' intermediate heat exchanger, allowing for the decoupling of the stream reinjection conditions from the saturation ones. Table II shows some key parameters for the different configurations analyzed. Because the high-temperature electrolysis process requires mostly electrical power and the extracted steam flow rates are quite limited, the plant configuration was chosen with extraction at the MSR inlet and return at the deareator inlet (IP/LT-DEA). This combination shows the lowest Power Loss Factor (PLF), defined as the penalization of gross electric power normalized to the thermal power extracted ($PLF = (P_{Design} - P_{OD}) / (Q_{Extracted})$). It is also the one with the lowest steam extraction temperature, which would be achievable even using a conventional pressurized water reactor. However, with a LFR, the same temperature is reached at a lower expansion stage, allowing a net gain in terms of electrical power generated.

Table II. Output comparison for different configurations.

Parameter	HP/HT- DEA	IP/LT- DEA	IP/HT- DEA	HP/HT- COND	IP/LT- COND	IP/HT- COND
Power-loss factor	0.499	0.349	0.372	0.592	0.448	0.459
H ₂ production rate (t/h)	2.79	2.88	2.87	2.75	2.82	2.81
SOE size (MW _{el})	109.04	112.34	111.81	107.10	110.14	109.9
Extracted steam (kg/s)	10.86	12.95	11.03	10.98	13.07	11.16
Extracted thermal power (MW _{th})	23.58	24.29	24.18	23.16	23.82	23.76

3.3. Partial load conditions of the selected system configuration

In this section, the variations of some system variables under conditions of part-load operation of the SOE units are presented. Figure 3 shows the trend of the net electrical output as function of the thermal power extracted for the different extraction and re-injection points in combination with the SOE's electric consumption curve. The intersection points of the two curves determine the potential operating

Figure 3. Net electric output for different extraction and re-injection points and SOE electrical consumption.

points of the integrated system as well as the size of the SOE. It is worth noting that even when the extracted power is below its nominal value, the relative ranking of the various extraction and reinjection point combinations remains unchanged in terms of the resulting net electric power.

In Figure 4 the T-Q diagrams for the combined 'Top-Aftercooler' and 'Bottom' heat exchangers of the intermediate circuit are shown at different load levels for the cells. Under nominal conditions, the temperature differences at the pinch points of the two heat exchangers are set to be 15°C and 38°C respectively. To obtain a preliminary assessment of the hybrid system's flexibility—namely, its ability to operate efficiently at reduced loads—it is also essential to examine key thermodynamic parameters of the intermediate loop. Modulation of hydrogen production is obtained by regulating both the mass flow rate of the intermediate fluid and of the extracted steam, resulting in a lower heat exchanged and lower SOE feedwater. As the mass flow rate of the intermediate circuit is reduced, the hot leg temperature is kept constant at 230°C while the cold leg one varies according to the characteristic curve of the Bottom heat exchanger. Despite a 75% SOE load reduction, the pinch point temperature difference of the 'Top-Aftercooler' heat exchanger remains unchanged, whereas the one of the 'Bottom' heat exchanger decreases to almost 15°C, which can be still considered a safe margin. From Figure

Figure 4. T-Q diagrams for different extraction conditions for 'Top-Aftercooler' (left figure) and 'Bottom' (right figure) intermediate loop heat exchangers.

4, the effect of the heat losses along the intermediate pipeline is also visible, which varies as the heat extraction is changed. The temperature drop between 'Top' heat exchanger outlet and 'Bottom' heat exchanger inlet (and vice versa) increases as the mass flow rate of the intermediate fluid is reduced.

4. CONCLUSION

The coupling analysis of an advanced nuclear reactor with solid oxide electrolysis for hydrogen production has made it possible to investigate and highlight how the design choices of the BOP can influence the performance of the plant in cogeneration mode. Extracting steam at the moisture separator reheater outlet and returning it at the deaerator inlet is the suggested option, yielding a hydrogen production capacity of 2.87 t/h and a power-loss factor of 0.372. Although not the configuration with the best performance, it is the one that guarantees the highest reliability to the plant, regardless of the amount of thermal power extracted. At the same time, the most critical aspects related to the thermal interface between the BOP and the external user have been analyzed. Also by significantly reducing the SOE load, the most critical pinch point in the 'Bottom' heat exchanger remains within acceptable limits. Future studies will focus on BOP configurations with increasingly higher extracted powers, multiple extraction points at different conditions, and dynamic analysis to account for variable electrical and thermal demands.

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